

Effect Of Percutaneous Transvenous Mitral Commissurotomy on Right Ventricular Function

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ABSTRACT:

Objective: To determine the pre and post changes in right ventricular function among patients subjected to percutaneous mitral valve commissurotomy for mitral stenosis.

Methodology: A quasi experimental study was carried out from 09 April 2021 to 09 Oct, 2021. TTE was performed at baseline and PTMC was done in all patients. After PTMC, all patients were kept in CCU for next 24 hours and another TTE was performed at 24th hour after PTMC for measuring changes in the RV function in terms of RVSP, RVOT-FS, RV TEi index, RV wall thickness, pulmonary artery systolic pressure.

Results: As per changes in RV parameters before PTMC and 24 hours PTMC, mean and SDs for RVSAP was 5.70 ± 4.50 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RVOT-FS was -1.22 ± 3.02 with P Value 0.003. Mean and SDs for RV ETi index was 0.14 ± 0.015 with P Value

0.000. Mean and SDs for RV wall thickness was 0.10 ± 0.03 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for pulmonary artery systolic pressure was 17.099 ± 4.20 with P Value 0.000.

Conclusion: This study has demonstrated that PTMC has significant effect on pre and post changes in right ventricular function amongst patients subjected to percutaneous mitral valve commissurotomy for mitral stenosis.

Keywords: Atrial Fibrillation, Echocardiography, Mitral Stenosis

INTRODUCTION:

Rheumatic Mitral stenosis (rMS), the most common cause of mitral valve stenosis (MVS) worldwide, leads to increase LA pressure (pressure overload), decreased forward flow to the LV, and eventually to pulmonary hypertension and heart failure symptoms. Initially, patients with MS in sinus rhythm (SR) manage to compensate flow impediment from the LA to the LV with an increase in LA dimensions associated with augmented LA contraction (Frank-Starling mechanism), which maintains LA total emptying volume². Eventually, LA remodeling develops resulting from tachycardia and the chronic pressure overload, which trigger several histological changes in the LA, including hypertrophy, necrosis, apoptosis, and fibrosis, and promoting the development of AF³.

Mitral valve stenosis symptoms may appear or worsen anytime your heart rate increases, such as during exercise. An episode of rapid heartbeats may accompany these symptoms. Or they may be triggered by pregnancy or other body stress, such as an infection. In mitral valve stenosis, pressure that builds up in the heart is then sent back to the lungs, resulting in fluid buildup (congestion) and shortness of breath⁴. Almost all cases of mitral stenosis are due to disease in the heart secondary to rheumatic fever and the consequent rheumatic heart disease. Uncommon causes of mitral stenosis are calcification of the mitral valve leaflets, and as a form of congenital heart disease. However, there are primary causes of mitral stenosis that emanate from a cleft mitral valve. It is the most common valvular heart disease in pregnancy⁵.

Other causes include infective endocarditis where the vegetation's may favor increase of stenosis. Other rare causes include mitral annular calcification, endomyocardial fibroelastosis, malignant carcinoid syndrome, systemic lupus erythematosus, Whipple disease, fabry disease, and rheumatoid arthritis. hurler' disease, hunter's disease, amyloidosis⁶.

The RV function is an important determinant of clinical symptoms, exercise capacity, pre-operative survival and postoperative outcome in these patients⁷. MS leads to increase in left atrial pressure due to the back pressure, results in passive rise in pulmonary venous and arterial pressures and causes RV dysfunction. RV dysfunction is also due to rheumatic process when it involves the myocardium, thus directly impairs RV function.

Since its introduction in 1984 by Inoue et al . PTMC is a safe and effective treatment for rheumatic MS and is treatment of choice in patients with a favorable anatomy. PTMC has been performed regularly in many cardiac centers for the over two decades¹⁰ however, the data on impact of PTMC on RV function remains scarce. In one study, mean right ventricular systolic pressure (RVSP) pre PTMC was significantly higher 62.3110.91 mm of Hg than that of post PTMC 24 hour's 57.5119.67 mm of Hg and post PTMC 06 moths 46.4917.8mm of Hg. In another study, immediately following PTMC, mitral valve area increased from baseline of 0.711 0.15 cm² to 1.84 1 0.17 cm², RV out-flow tract fractional shortening (RVOT—FS) increased

from $33.94 \pm 7.55\%$ to $37.33 \pm 7.67\%$. There was a significant decrease in systolic pulmonary artery pressure from 48.93 ± 13.08 mmHg to 29.56 ± 7.71 . RV Tei- index decreased from 0.47 ± 0.12 to 0.32 ± 0.11 . In another study, pre and post PTMC statistics for right ventricle were RV wall thickness (6.16 ± 0.91 vs 6.06 ± 0.79 mm), and RV TEi index (0.56 ± 0.08 vs 0.4 ± 0.08)¹⁴. In another study, TTE performed before PTMC showing mean mitral valve area $0.9\text{cm} \times 0.24\text{cm}$. TTE 24 hours after PTMC showed mean left atrial diameter $4.68 \times 3.1\text{cm}$, mean mitral valve area $2.167 \times 0.71\text{cm}$, mean mitral valve gradient 5.42×4.6 mm of Hg, mean right ventricular systolic pressure (RVSP) 43 ± 18.41 mm of Hg. After follow up for one year, 8.79% patients developed signs and symptoms of congestive heart failure. Of these, 10(3.25%) patients were found to have right ventricular dysfunction. Mean RVSP 24 hours post PTMC was 63 ± 10.21 mm of Hg, mean LA

MATERIALS & METHODS:

A quasi-experimental study was carried out from 09 April 2021 to 09 Oct, 2021 at the Department of Cardiology, MTI-Hayatabad Medical Complex, Peshawar using non probability consecutive technique. All patients meeting the inclusion criteria (MS with minimum duration of one year) was included in the study through OPD department. The purpose and benefits of the study was explained to all patients and a written informed consent was obtained. Sample size was 60 based on following assumptions Mean pulmonary artery systolic pressure before

diameter $5.18 \pm 1.82\text{cm}$ and mean LVEF $50.14\% \pm 5.825$.

The present study was designed to determine the effect of right ventricular function before and after PTMC for MS. PTMC is regularly performed in our hospital settings and due to long term follow up advised to the patients where most of patient don't show up, the effect of PTMC on survival due to changes in RV function. Remains a question. Moreover, despite of more than 2 decades of performing PTMC, local studies on its effect on RV function are extremely rare. This study provided us with local statistics about the magnitude of changes that occur in the RV function after PTMC compared to baseline. The results of this study will be published in local literature and will add more scientific knowledge in the body of literature along with future research recommendations.

PTMC: 48.93 ± 13.08 Mean pulmonary artery systolic pressure 24 hours after PTMC: 29.56 ± 7.71 Threshold probability for rejecting null hypothesis (two tailed alpha): 0.05 Probability of failing to reject null hypothesis (Beta): 0.05, Power: 80% All patients were subjected to detailed history, followed by complete routine examination. TTE was performed at baseline and PTMC was done in all patients. After PTMC, all patients were kept in CCU for next 24 hours and another TTE was performed at 24th hour after PTMC for measuring changes in the RV function in terms of RVSP, RVOT-FS, RV TEi

index, RV wall thickness, pulmonary artery systolic pressure. All the ECHO and PTMC procedures was done by single experienced cardiologist having minimum of five years of experience.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data was stored and analyzed in SPSS version 23 for windows. Mean \pm SD was calculated for numerical variables like age, height, weight, BMI, baseline and follow up RV parameters (RVSP, RVOT-FS, RV TEi index, RV wall thickness, pulmonary artery systolic pressure). Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables like gender, history of hypertension, diabetes, presence or absence of AF, stage of MS. Paired sample T test was applied to determine the significance of RV parameter changes from baseline to follow up

with p value of 0.05 as significant. Changes in RV parameters was checked against age, gender, BMI, history of hypertension, diabetes, AF at presentation to see the effect modifications. All results were presented in the form of tables and graphs.

RESULT:

As per changes in RV parameters before PTMC and 24 hours PTMC, mean and SDs for RVSP was 5.70 ± 4.50 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RVOT-FS was -1.22 ± 3.02 with P Value 0.003. Mean and SDs for RV ETi index was 0.14 ± 0.015 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RV wall thickness was 0.10 ± 0.03 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for pulmonary artery systolic pressure 17.099 ± 4.20 with P Value 0.000.

Table: 1 Changes in RV Parameters on Transthoracic Echocardiography at Baseline (Before PTMC) And Follow Up (24 Hours After PTMC) (n=60)

RV Parameters	Changes in RV Parameters		P Value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	
RVSP (mmHg)	5.70000	4.50322	.000
RVOT-FS (%)	-1.22667	3.02956	.003
RV TEI Index	.14183	.01535	.000
Wall Thickness (mm)	.10300	.03132	.000
Pulmonary Artery Systolic Pressure (mmHg)	17.99933	4.20138	.000

DISCUSSION:

Rheumatic Mitral stenosis (rMS), the most common cause of mitral valve stenosis (MVS) worldwide, leads to increase LA pressure (pressure overload), decreased forward flow to the LV, and eventually to pulmonary

hypertension and heart failure symptoms. Initially, patients with MS in sinus rhythm (SR) manage to compensate flow impediment from the LA to the LV with an increase in LA dimensions associated with augmented LA contraction (Frank-Starling mechanism), which

maintains LA total emptying volume¹⁶. Eventually, LA remodeling develops resulting from tachycardia and the chronic pressure overload, which trigger several histological changes in the LA, including hypertrophy, necrosis, apoptosis, and fibrosis, and promoting the development of AF¹⁷.

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atrial pressure due to the back pressure, results in passive rise in pulmonary venous and arterial pressures and causes RV dysfunction. RV dysfunction is also due to rheumatic process when it involves the myocardium, thus directly impairs RV function.

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4.6813.1cm, mean mitral valve area 2.167 ± 0.71 cm², mean mitral valve gradient 5.42 ± 4.6 mm of Hg, mean right ventricular systolic pressure (RVSP) 43 ± 18.41 mm of Hg. After follow up for one year, 8.79% patients developed signs and symptoms of congestive heart failure. Of these, 10(3.25%) patients were found to have right ventricular dysfunction. Mean RVSP 24 hours post PTMC was 63 ± 10.21 mm of Hg, mean LA diameter 5.18 ± 1.82 cm and mean LVEF 50.14 ± 5.82 . This was in consistent to the findings of this study, where, as per changes in RV parameters before PTMC and 24 hours PTMC, mean and SDs for RVSAP was 5.70 ± 4.50 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RVOT-FS was -1.22 ± 3.02 with P Value 0.003. Mean and SDs for RV ETi index was 0.14 ± 0.015 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RV wall thickness was 0.10 ± 0.03 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for pulmonary artery systolic pressure 17.099 ± 4.20 with P Value 0.000.

It is obvious from the literature that, MS predominantly affects a younger population, and the majority of symptomatic MS patients usually present before the age of 30 years and our findings are in agreement with these studies. On the other hand, in Western countries, the disease primarily involves the older population as shown in a series of PTMC reported from developed countries. In addition, reports indicate that the progression of symptoms of rheumatic MS in this part of the world is very rapid. In an earlier study, >85% of the patients were in functional Class

III/IV at the time of presentation. The age distribution and female preponderance of our patients were similar to other studies from developing countries.^[17,18]

PTMC using the Inoue technique was first reported by Inoue *et al.* in 1984.^[9] Since then, it has evolved and rapidly became the standard technique for the management of MS with pliable valves. The results of PTMC in adults are similar to that of open commissurotomy and better than that of closed commissurotomy. Studies have found that PTMC with use of simple height-based balloon sizing method in the step-wise Inoue balloon approach is associated with excellent short-term and long-term efficacy rates and a low risk of creating severe mitral regurgitation. The present study reported statistically significant difference between pre- and post-procedure as per changes in RV parameters before PTMC and 24 hours PTMC, mean and SDs for RVSAP was 5.70 ± 4.50 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RVOT-FS was -1.22 ± 3.02 with P Value 0.003. Mean and SDs for RV ETi index was 0.14 ± 0.015 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for RV wall thickness was 0.10 ± 0.03 with P Value 0.000. Mean and SDs for pulmonary artery systolic pressure 17.099 ± 4.20 with P Value 0.000. The results of the present study are similar to the above results. In accordance with the above, the patients in the study cohort had a demonstrable increase in their performance on the treadmill after PTMC. This was not uniformly correlated to the valve area but was related to pre-PTMC physical statistics and the

well-known variable hemodynamic effects of flow and valve area.

Many patients of MS present with respiratory symptoms. The chronic changes in the pulmonary circulation are secondary to increased pulmonary venous pressure and reflex pulmonary artery vasoconstriction. Accumulation of water, proteins, and proteoglycans in the interstitium of the lungs are the basis of the clinical manifestations of MS and can be detected by pulmonary function tests also the residual volume function may be altered due to an increase in the left atrial pressure. Few recent studies have shown that successful PTMC immediately improves cardiac and pulmonary function along with the clinical status of patients with MS.

The present study has certain limitations. The sample size was rather small, and no long follow-up could be done due to the limitation of time for our study. Hence, future studies with larger sample and longer follow-up are suggested.

CONCLUSION:

This study has demonstrated that PTMC has significant effect on pre and post changes in right ventricular function amongst patients subjected to percutaneous mitral valve commissurotomy for mitral stenosis and therefore, it is recommended that proper assessment should be carried out routinely in all such cases of severe mitral stenosis. The significant changes in post-PTMC may be an indication for offering PTMC at an earlier stage to those patients whose quality of life has been

severely compromised due to severe mitral stenosis.

Declaration by Authors

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Author's contribution:

Following authors have made substantial contributions to the manuscript as under:

MAK: Literature search, data collection, write-up

SK: Literature search, Conceptualization of study design, data collection.

TS: Data collection, data analysis, data interpretation

SMS: Proof readings, write-up.

Authors agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

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